

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The Epimetheus Project: Searching for new authentic 'contactees' and the scientific information received from Extraterrestrial Intelligences

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Abstract

The recent American congressional hearing was carried out after the Pentagon admitted the authenticity of encounters of UFOs (Unidentified Flying Objects) with jets and released an unclassified version of a report investigating several cases. Previously in the Final Contact Project (FCP) investigating the probability of the authenticity of a series of alleged 'contactees' in Close Encounters of the Fifth Kind (CE5thK) and using an original approach, we found evidence to support that in some CE5thK advanced contact with Extraterrestrial Intelligences (ETI) with human beings is probably happening. In this study, the Epimetheus Project (EP), with a new team of researchers and using the same twelve-criteria method as the prior FCP, investigated a new series of 66 alleged CE5thK from the world, compared the results to the previous FCP, and present original variables from both studies. In the EP, we found 52 cases to have a low probability of authenticity, one case to be inconclusive evidence, and 13 cases having a high probability of being an authentic phenomenon. In comparison to FCP, the EP study had a significantly lower rate of cases of high probability of being authentic (19.7% vs. 34.755 respectively, $p=0.048$). In addition, we discuss the meaning of these results, and the information received in these CE5thK cases of high probability of being authentic, also including original information from both studies, such as historical characters cited, existence of intraterrestrial life, parallel worlds, and time travel. Our study confirmed that advanced contact from ETI with human beings on the Earth is occurring. The richness of new technical and scientific information received by authentic 'contactees' could represent a means of 'technology' transfer, with revolutionary potential for our society to develop and apply these benefits to the critical problems that risk mankind's extinction.

Keywords: Abduction; Close encounters; Contactees; Extraterrestrial intelligence; Technology transfer; Unidentified flying object

1. Introduction

In the recent American congressional hearing, Pentagon officials testified, and admitted the authenticity of encounters of UFOs (Unidentified Flying Objects) with jets. An unclassified version of a report investigating several cases was released admitting that the vast majority of the cases did not originate from American military or other advanced US government technology [1]. In December 2017, three videos of UFOs were published by the New York Times and "To

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the Stars Academy of Arts and Science“, a self-described public benefit corporation. The first of the videos, known as the “GIMBAL footage” shows a 2004 encounter near San Diego between a Navy fighter jet and an Unidentified Aerial Phenomenon (UAP) [2]. In June, 2021, the Pentagon admitted the authenticity of these encounters and released an unclassified version of a report investigating 144 cases by the US Defense Department’s Advanced Aerospace Threat Identification Program (AATIP), an agency created in 2007 but only publicly known in 2017. American intelligence officials still cannot explain the unusual movements of the aerial phenomena witnessed by Navy pilots in recent years. These have mystified scientists and the military, according to senior administration officials briefed on the findings of the highly anticipated government report. The report determined that the vast majority of more than 144 incidents over the past two decades did not originate from any American military or other advanced U.S. government technology, the officials said [3]. The report concedes that much about the observed phenomena remains difficult to explain, including their acceleration, as well as ability to change direction and submerge. Some of the incidents were recorded on video, including one taken by a plane’s camera in early 2015, that shows an object zooming over the ocean waves, which caused the pilots to question what they were watching. With the public asking more questions about UFOs, more officials appear willing to answer them. “There are a lot more sightings than have been made public,” John Ratcliffe, the former director of national intelligence, told Fox News in March. Quite a few of them, he said, “are difficult to explain.” John Brennan, the former director of the C.I.A., said on a podcast last year that some of the unexplained sightings might be “some type of phenomenon that is the result of something that we don’t yet understand and that could involve some type of activity that some might say constitutes a different form of life.” [4].

In the past, the negative attitudes about the possibility of extraterrestrial intelligences (ETI) coming into contact with humankind was due to several factors. At first, the presence of logical problems unsolved such as the Fermi Paradox, that is, the apparent contradiction between high estimates of the probability of the existence of ETI and the lack of evidence for, or contact with, such civilizations [5]. Second, the official reports from governmental agencies as the Condon Report [6], which concluded that there was no evidence that UFOs were extraterrestrial spacecraft and that further study was not justified [7]. And third, the opinion by astronomers and other experts in the world [8, 9] published in the 70’s assuring the impossibility of that contact pointing out biological, astronomical distances, and technical difficulties. However, at present, there is evidence from several fields about the possibility that ETI could have contacted humankind, challenging the mainstream of science that denies the possibility of this contact is happening. First, there is archaeological and historical evidence suggesting the possibility that Earth was visited in ancient times by ETI. Ancient extraterrestrial theorists believe that thousands of years ago, ETI landed on Earth where they were hailed as gods and helped shape human civilization [10]. Second, some researchers have revisited the Fermi Paradox. Freitas affirmed that the assertion that ETI do not exist rests upon an unproven and untenable presumption: that ETI are currently not present in the Solar System [11]. The current observational status of the Solar System is insufficient to support the assumption that ETI are not here. Furthermore, there is the high probability of contact expressed by the Drake equation that is used to estimate the number of detectable ETI in the Milky Way galaxy [12]. It is acknowledged that we have already announced our existence via radio broadcasts to any nearby technological civilizations. To not anticipate contact with an ETI would be unwise.

Before the 2021 Pentagon report, previous efforts to shed light on the reality of UFOs had its epic moment in 1978. Prominent academics and UFO researchers Allen Hynek and Jacques Vallee approached the United Nations with the suggestion to set up an international office of investigators and researchers to coordinate international scientific research into UFOs, and to inform the Secretary-General of the observations, research, and evaluation of such studies. The UN General Assembly responded favorably by adopting Decision GA /426. Unfortunately, nothing was done to bring the decision to fruition and it lies dormant to this very day [13]. In spite of these initiatives, interest of the scientific community in testing the possibility of interaction of ETI with human beings on our planet has been very scarce. The few published scientific works have been concerned with psychological and psychiatric analysis of cases involving individuals allegedly abducted by ETI, usually for purpose of examination or experimentation, named Close Encounters of the Fourth Kind (CE4). According to these studies, abduction narratives seem to proceed from internal sources, representing non-physical experiences of psychological origin inspired by publicized material, plus a significant number of hoaxes [14]. Studies concerning ‘contactees’ or people affirming having experienced a Close Encounters of Fifth Kind (CE5thK), defined as conscious contact with ETI with transmission of some information, are almost inexistent. Bartolomeu [15] pointed out that although there are few psychological studies of ‘contactees’ or ‘abductees’, virtually all of these individuals have been characterized as mentally disturbed or irrational. In the Final Contact Project, a milestone study in the field, we hypothesized that authentic Close Encounters of Fifth Kind (CE5thK) could probably be happening. We designed and applied an original approach with qualitative and quantitative variables constituting a rule of 12 criteria for defining a high probability, low probability or inconclusive evidence in order to set the authenticity of 72 cases of alleged CE5thK. A high probability was considered as authentic. We found 25 cases to be a high probability of being an authentic phenomenon. Thus, we found evidence to support that advanced contact from ETI with human beings probably is happening on the Earth at present. To our knowledge, this was the first time such findings were

reported. Our results were counter to mainstream science and astronomy, challenging the paradigm of the impossibility that mankind has been contacted by ETI [16]. Additionally, in these authentic CE5thK cases, there was important and far-reaching information with amazing potential for our society in several fields of knowledge. Information received by authentic ‘contactees’ was related to origin, motivations of these ETI, and even specific technical information.

In recent years, we perceived that the number of individuals publicly alleging ETI contact has increased substantially. The repercussions to society are increasing. It could be related to the greater openness to Ufology by the media and public entities. The objective of this work was first to apply the original approach of the FCP using a new trained team of researchers with a new series of alleged ‘contactees’ in order to find new ‘contactees’ of high probability of being authentic. Second, to compare the results of this series with that of FCP. We hypothesized in the EP study that authentic CE5thK cases could be continuing, but its rate would be lower than in the FCP and this might be associated with modern communications. In addition, when we identified and confirmed new authentic ‘contactees’, we characterize and discuss the information received by them in light of the results of the previous FCP study, including new variables from both studies.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Definition of CE5thK

In order to better understand the UFO phenomenon, Hynek classified the cases of supposed contact with UFOs into three categories of Close Encounters [17]. He defined Close Encounters of the First Kind (CE1) as strange objects seen nearby but without physical interaction with the environment. Close Encounters of the Second Kind (CE2) are defined as a CE1 case that leaves physical evidence, e.g. soil depressions, vegetation damage or causes electromagnetic interference. Close Encounters of the Third Kind (CE3) are defined as CE1stK or CE2ndK cases where occupants or entities are seen. After that, other researchers [18] defined the abduction phenomenon as Close Encounter of Fourth Kind (CE4). ‘Abductee’ is someone kidnapped by ETI, usually for the purpose of examination and experimentation and often with a lapse of memory for the period they were held captive (missing time). Finally, several writers defined the CE5 [19], but the definitions are not consistent. Therefore, we defined for our study that ‘CE5thK’ involves a more advanced contact of a witness named a ‘contactee’ that consciously recalls having been contacted physically or mentally, dialoguing and receiving transmission of some kind of information from the ETI [16].

2.2. The Epimetheus Project

Dr. Acosta-Navarro from the Latin American Academy of Scientific Ufology (LAASU) designed the Epimetheus Project (EP) in February 2016 in Sao Paulo, Brazil, as a follow-on to the FCP, and aimed to research a new series of alleged cases of CE5thK. Dr. Acosta-Navarro is a university professor from the School of Medicine of Sao Paulo University. He is a medical doctor holding a PhD degree in Medical Sciences and has a second PhD degree in Social Sciences, both from the Sao Paulo University. Additionally, he has 44 years of experience in the Ufology field having researched more than one hundred alleged CE5thK cases (Fig 1).

Figure 1 Team of field research about the ‘contactee’ VlaK case (Vlado Kapetanovich with pseudonym Vitko Novi) in the “Central Hidroeléctrica de Huallanca” (3,540 m. above sea level), place of the first contact. They are Jaime Valdivia (left), Dr. Julio Acosta-Navarro (middle) and Mr. Hugo Acosta (right), Huaraz, Peru, January 2008

After the publication of the FCP, some academic centers from Latin America, such as the Heart Institute of Sao Paulo University (Brazil) and School Pharmacy, San Marcos University, (Peru), some Brazilian governmental entities such as the *Assembleia Legislativa do Estado de São Paulo* and *Camara Municipal de São Paulo* [20], and other publications [21, 22] gave attention to it. Dr. Acosta-Navarro and the task force from the FCP became a non-governmental organization non-profit recognized by the Justice Ministry of Brazil. In 2019, this organization launched the “LAASU Manifest: Extraterrestrials contact human beings” at an international meeting in Sao Paulo (“*Encontro Internacional de Exopolitica: O fenomeno OVNI rumo as Nações Unidas*”), directed to public entities, mass media, the general public, and international organizations [23]. (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Team of members of the Latin American Academy of Scientific Ufology (LAASU), a non-governmental organization non-profit in the Auditorium of the “*Camara Municipal de São Paulo*”, a public governmental entity during the meeting “*Seminário Científico: OVNIS, o misterio do século XX desvendado...!*”, in São Paulo, Brazil, April 27th, 2019

The name Epimetheus of this project came from the Greek god, who was a younger brother of the other more famous god, Prometheus, meaning metaphorically that this was a brother project of the Final Contact Project. A new multidisciplinary team of 14 professionals and technical experts with experience and interest in Ufology and correlated areas was trained by Dr. Acosta-Navarro to carry out the research following the designed approach established previously by the Final Contact Project. We used purposive sampling again (also known as judgment, selective or subjective sampling), a sampling technique in which the researcher relies on his or her own judgment. It was included in the study several cases of alleged CE5thK (non-science fiction or non-hoax at the preliminary evaluation by Dr. Acosta-Navarro) that met the following two inclusion criterion: 1. Availability of enough and trustable sources of information in order to arrive a definite conclusion. 2. Publicly known after 1947, the modern age of UFOs. Information obtained from primary sources of each alleged CE5thK included face-to-face interviews or e-mail communications, social network communications, or when the alleged ‘contactee’ was dead, familial interviews and e-mail information. When it was possible, audio or video recording and transcriptions were used. Secondary sources included books, journals, websites, YouTube, and social networks, which were also used during the time this research was being conducted. The period of research applying the final design was from February 2016 until October 2021.

2.3. Design of study

The design of the study was prospective, analytical, and comparative. We considered quantitative and qualitative research as was described previously in more detail in the FCP [16]. In brief, the first step was establishing a set of valid criteria that should be used in order to set the authenticity of the alleged CE5thK because the concept of truth is discussed and debated in several contexts, including philosophy and religion. Various theories and viewpoints of truth continue to be debated among scholars and philosophers [24]. We designed an original approach in order to determine the truth or authenticity of each case. It was the result of empirical knowledge coming from more than one hundred cases of alleged CE5thK in several decades of research and adaptations of the classical criteria about how to establish the truth. The theoretical framework included the content analysis of information from alleged CE5thK cases to systematically organize data into a structured format. Each case was assigned and analyzed at least by two researchers. After each researcher had analyzed all the information available about each case independently, the case was presented to the team, debated and concluded in a general meeting of experts. We emphasized the importance of more than one researcher in order to minimize experimenter bias. The use of experts’ consensus as a tool to establish the case authenticity is justified here due to absence of other kind of evidence. It is an accepted practice in other areas of

knowledge, such as diagnosis and therapeutic medicine decisions. Frances believes this survey method is probably the best available means for standardizing practice for decision points not well covered by research [25].

2.4. Twelve criteria-rule

As described in the Final Contact Project, the EP used an evaluation tool containing qualitative and quantitative variables constituting a rule of twelve criteria to be applied to each case for defining if an alleged CE5thK has high probability (technically authentic or true) or low probability (technically non-authentic) of being authentic. The presence of any criterion gives a score of one point and its absence gives a score of zero. A higher score increases the chances to reach the cutoff threshold for being considered as high probability of being authentic. The rationale of using an approach with criteria based in long empirical knowledge is accepted in other areas of knowledge such as medicine, for example, Jones' criteria in order to diagnose Rheumatic Fever [26].

Subjective and objective criteria were set in the rule of twelve criteria as follows.

2.4.1. Subjective criteria

- Consistency. Absence of substantial contradictions in the description of the events and maintenance of the same story as a real experience during the entire life of alleged 'contactee'.
- Coherency/Logic of account. Overall sense of understandability, logical and orderly and consistent relation of parts. Transparency of the information and logical sequence of the reported story. All pertinent facts must be arranged in a consistent and cohesive fashion as an integrated whole.
- Pragmatism. Disposition of alleged 'contactee' in giving all the information related to events with no evidence suggesting elusive behavior avoiding specific details of the reported story.
- New contribution. Presence of information suggesting substantial new intellectual or scientific contribution in the story content that was not probably created or originated from the abilities or knowledge of the alleged 'contactee'.
- Sensorial perception. Experience involving objective and sensorial perception by any of the five senses, not restricted exclusively to psychological-mental experiences from alleged 'contactee'.
- Intuition /experience of researcher. Integral judgment facing the subjective and objective criteria and applying the experience and intuition of researcher for determining each case as authentic or not.

Objective criteria

- Presence of other witnesses in the main ufologic event.
- Paranormality. Presence of any witnessed abnormal phenomena (telepathy, teletransport, telekinesis, clairvoyance, or curation not explainable by coincidence or other ordinary causes).
- Presence of physical evidence of the event such as photography, films or other objects that can be analyzed by others researchers, without indications of hoax.
- Presence of bodily evidence (injury, scar, burns or implants) or other physical evidence (including implants) in the alleged 'contactee' resulting from contact.
- Predicted contact of UFO phenomenon. It is deemed valid only if the announcement of a next contact was made beforehand to other people, such as a journalist, scientist or other witnesses in the general public, and the contact was confirmed afterwards. We did not consider as valid any account of a predicted contact that was retrospective only and having the 'contactee' as the only witness.
- Later scientific proof of any technical or historical information or technological device described by the alleged 'contactee' that afterwards was confirmed, discovered or developed by humanity later, suggesting an advanced knowledge in relation to that date.

After the presentation and discussion of each alleged CE5thK case, the researchers responsible for each case defined in mutual consensus what category the case should fall into. In the case of no consensus between two researchers, the case was reassigned to a third researcher to carry out a new cycle of presentation and discussion in order to get a conclusion. The analysis by more than one researcher had the objective of validating the findings of any individual researcher, minimizing bias and subjectivity.

2.5. Definition of authenticity

As described previously in the FCP, in order to define a case as "high probability" of being authentic (true) it was necessary that the case met all the six subjective criteria plus at least one objective criterion. We established this high cutoff threshold because we considered that in the context of this topic currently being controversial, we must choose

the strictest level of cutoff in order to accept an alleged CE5thK as true beyond reasonable doubt. The six subjective criteria convinced the researchers of the authenticity of case and the presence of at least one objective criterion gives the definite proof or worked as a way of internal validation. In addition, when we found a case true with a high score (10 to 12) we called it a 'super-contactee'. If a case had all the six criteria but none objective criteria, we considered it as "inconclusive evidence". A case was defined as "low probability" when the case presented five or less subjective criteria irrespective of the presence or absence of objective criteria.

2.6. Analysis of information in CE5thK of high probability to be authentic

In the second part of this research, we planned a complementary analysis of the CE5thK cases concluded as high probability to be authentic. The characterization and analysis of information in these authentic cases was based on a 98 question questionnaire embracing different topics: 'contactee', ufologic event, publication data, and a presence of information of technical, historical, philosophical, socio-economical, biological or other nature. Most of the questions were mainly categorical variables (yes/no). We compared the EP findings with the prior findings in the FCP with respect to concordant information received by 'contactees' from ETI such as following variables: origin of ETI, motivations of ETI visiting Earth, vegetarianism as dietetic pattern recommended, critics of capitalism or money-based system, reincarnation as real phenomenon, and presence of ETI among us. In addition, we analyzed specific original information less concordant from both studies not published previously. This complementary analysis included the following categorical variables: abduction phenomenon as part of 'contactee' experience, physical travel in a spacecraft by 'contactee', presence of a fine screen television device inside the spacecraft, existence of intraterrestrial beings or undersea bases, existence of civilizations unknown in mankind's past, known historical characters cited by ETI, lifespans of ETI longer than human beings, domain of artificial insemination by ETI, possibility of human body duplication or cloning, risk of overpopulation on Earth, eventual rescue of human beings in case of humanity's extinction, presence of human beings living on other planets, parallel worlds or dimensions as real phenomenon, 'stargate' or dimensional gates as real phenomenon, and time travel as a real phenomenon.

2.7. Ethics

As in the FCP, we did not consider necessary the informed consent of the alleged 'contactees' due to all these individuals had publicly assured having been contacted physically or mentally with an ETI and there was some information received from them, therefore this research is focused about a specific matter of public domain. Additionally some of alleged 'contactees' were not contacted by us directly and in others cases they were dead.

2.8. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis and description of results were presented as absolute numbers and percentages. Categorical variables (for example sex, continent of origin, source of information, presence of any specific information in authentic CE5thK), were summarized as percentages and continuous variables (for example age of 'contactee', year of publication) as mean \pm SD. The association between categorical variables was investigated by chi-square or Fisher exact tests for parametric distribution. We used the Mann-Whitney test for non-parametric distribution. Statistical significance was assumed for $P \leq 0.05$. All analyses were carried out using SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences).

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive analysis of total sampling

Ninety two cases of alleged CE5thK from several locations of the world were initially identified and registered. From these, 26 cases were excluded by insufficient sources of information and 66 cases were included in the study to be analyzed by two or more researchers. It was found that the period when the cases were publicly known was between 1954 and 2020.

Data about sex distribution, continent of origin, type of data source, main source of information (virtual or printed), still living or dead situation, year of publication and number of researchers by case are shown in Table 1. The data are compared with the FCP. There was no difference between either study with respect to sex distribution, continent of origin, type of data source, or number of researchers. Both studies had a predominance of masculine sex. Comparison of the 'main source of data' found that in the EP, the virtual sources were significantly higher than FCP and the rate of 'contactees' still being alive in the EP was higher than FCP. Likewise the mean of year of publication was significantly more recent in the EP, all three findings suggesting that the series from EP was more modern than the 'contactees' studied in the earlier FCP.

Table 1 Descriptive data from alleged ‘contactees’ in the CE5thK as a whole in the Epimetheus Project (n=66) and the Final Contact Project (n=72)

General data	Subcategory	Epimetheus Project (2022)	Final Contact Project (2016)	P value
Sex		N=67 ^a	n=74 ^b	
	Male	52 (77.6%)	60 (81.13%)	0.26
	Female	15 (22.4%)	14 (18.9%)	
Continent of origin		N=66	N=72	
	South America	50 (75.75%)	48 (66.7%)	0.06
	North America	13 (19.70%)	14 (19.4%)	
	Central America	1 (1.52%)	0	
	Europe	1 (1.52%)	8 (11.1%)	
	Asia	0	1 (1.4%)	
Africa	1 (1.52%)	1 (1.4%)		
Type of data source		N=66	N=72	
	Primary	23 (34.85%)	33 (45.8%)	0.15
	Secondary	43 (65.15%)	39 (54.2%)	
Main source of data		N=66	N=72	
	Printed	42 (63.64%)	69 (95.83%)	<0.001
	Virtual (networks)	24 (36.36%)	3 (4.17%)	
Still living –or–death situation		N=67	N=74	
	Still living	48 (71.64%)	40 (54.1%)	0.001
	Death	6 (8.96%)	26 (35.1%)	
	Unknown	13 (19.40%)	8 (10.8%)	
Year of publication of event (mean ± SEM)		N=66	N= 72	
		2002.59±2.03	1982.56±2.02	0.003
Number of researchers by case		N=66	N=72	
	Two	54 (81.82%)	56 (77.8%)	0.14
	Three or more	12 (18.18%)	16 (22.2%)	

^a In 66 cases of alleged CE5thK in the Epimetheus Project there was one case with 2 alleged ‘contactees’.

^b In 72 cases of alleged CE5thK in the Final Contact Project there were three cases with two main witnesses in each one. In one case from these, we do not have not all information from all witnesses.

3.2. Categorization of authenticity

Applying the approach based on the 12 criteria-rule, we tested the central hypotheses. In the EP, we found 52 cases of CE5thK to be low probability, one case to be inconclusive evidence, and 13 cases were found to be high probability of being an authentic phenomenon (Figure 3). This new series of EP subjects confirmed again that authentic CE5thK cases probably continue to happen on Earth.

Figure 3 The Epimetheus Project: Design of the study and main results.

The criteria scoring from each case identified by codename and country of origin, are shown in Tables 2 and 3. Scores varied between 7 to 11 points for the cases of high probability (Table 2), six points for the one case with inconclusive evidence, and 1 to 6 points for the cases of low probability of being authentic (Table 3).

Table 2 The Epimetheus Project: Scoring of CE5thK cases concluded as High Probability to be Authentic (n=13) ^a

CASE	COUNTRY	SC1	SC2	SC3	SC4	SC5	SC6	OC1	OC2	OC3	OC4	OC5	OC6	SCORE
R-Gonza	Peru	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	10
A-Uchoa	Brazil	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	10
Benj-Parr	Argentina	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	9
Avalo	Peru	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	9
Maur_Adv	Brazil	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	9
Most-F	Bolivia	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	9
Prof-Lu	Brazil	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	8
On-Pate	Brazil	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	8
Fak-Broth	Brazil	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	8
Valda	SouthAfrica	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	8
Brot-Ph	USA	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	7
O-Rimx	Costa Rica	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	7
Osor	Peru	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	7

^a SC1: Consistency; SC2: Coherency/Logic; SC3: Pragmatism; SC4: New contribution; SC5: Sensorial perception; SC6: Intuition/Experience; OC1: Other witnesses; OC2: Paranormality; OC3: Physical evidence; OC4: Body evidence; OC5: Predicted contact; OC6: Scientific proof.

Table 3 The Epimetheus Project: Scoring of CE5thK cases concluded as Inconclusive Evidence (n=1) and Low Probability of being Authentic (n=52) ^a

CASE	COUNTRY	SC1	SC2	SC3	SC4	SC5	SC6	OC1	OC2	OC3	OC4	OC5	OC6	SCORE
Inconclusive evidence														
Ang-L	USA	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
Low Probability														
StaRo	USA	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	6
Tom	USA	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	5
Rmth	USA	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	5
O-Alv	Brazil	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
Coer	USA	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
Strib	USA	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
Her-Us	Brazil	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
PreNic	USA	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
Bshr	USA	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
Profet	Brazil	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
Lact	Sweden	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
Orls	Brazil	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
A-Rapha	USA	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
Coma-E	Brazil	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
Pol-N	Brazil	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
Voz-I	Brazil	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
VanBir	Brazil	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
LyR	USA	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
Blu-Bok	USA	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
Pgio	Brazil	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
Al-R	Brazil	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
Um-Is	Brazil	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
Edu	Brazil	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
Am-Res	Colombia	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
Stel	Brazil	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
Nil-B	Brazil	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
Mr.Cas	Brazil	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
JeSe	Brazil	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
FK	Barzil	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Procy	Brazil	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
SIRj	Brazil	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2

Rog-F	Brazil	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Ztha	Brazil	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Ib-Up	Brazil	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Ros-Ma	Venezuela	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
JoCa	Brazil	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
La-Fon	Brazil	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Ja-How	Brazil	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Goul	Brazil	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
LiFe	Brazil	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Evang	Brazil	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Ro-B	Brazil	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
TedH	Brazil	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
E-Roch	Brazil	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
CGOD	USA	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Ario	Brazil	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Ka-R	Brazil	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Ish	Brazil	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
AV	Brazil	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
MuMe	Brazil	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Cid-M	Brazil	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1

^a SC1: Consistency; SC2: Coherency/Logic; SC3: Pragmatism; SC4: New contribution; SC5: Sensorial perception; SC6: Intuition/Experience; OC1: Other witnesses; OC2: Paranormality; OC3: Physical evidence; OC4: Body evidence; OC5: Predicted contact; OC6: Scientific proof.

In contrast with the results from the FCP, where 25 (34.7%) cases were found to have a high probability of being an authentic phenomenon, in this EP study we found the rate of high probability to be authentic was lower (19.70%). When comparing the 2 categories of cases of high probability of being authentic vs. the two other categories (low probability and inconclusive evidence) in the EP and FCP, the rate of authentic cases is significantly lower in the EP ($p=0.048$). (Table 4).

Table 4 Comparative distribution of cases of alleged ‘contactees’ from CE5thK in two categories from the Epimetheus Project and the Final Contact Project

Categories	Epimetheus Project (n=66)	Final Contact Project (n=72)	Total	P value
Low probability to be authentic+ Inconclusive evidence	53 (80.30%)	47 (65.28%)	100	
High probability to be authentic	13 (19.70%)	25 (34.72%)	37	0.048
Total	66 (100%)	72 (100%)	137	

Pearson $\chi^2 = 3.8960$

When we separated the authentic CE5thK ‘contactees’ into two categories according to scoring, authentic ‘contactees’ scoring 7 to 9 points, and those we called ‘super-contactees’ scoring 10 to 12, we found six ‘super-contactees’ in the FCP and two in the EP.

3.3. Brief description of two authentic CE5thK cases

3.3.1. First case: Uchoa (Brazil)

General Alfredo M. Uchoa (1906-1996) served in the Brazilian Army as a Professor and as an Engineer where he taught Mathematics and Physics for 20 years. During his earlier years had already encountered a number of situations and phenomena that orthodox science was unable to explain. These caused him to develop an interest in parapsychology and, eventually, UFOs. In 1968 on a plantation in Alexania near of Brasilia that many people considered haunted, Uchoa and his team of investigators, after exhaustive inquiries, came to the same conclusion. Those vigils or expeditions were attended by many professionals in the medical field, law, and military. They all were able to witness and register their testimonies of numerous UFO phenomena. In visits to other places together with Mr. Wilson da Silva, an alleged 'contactee' of the region that received advice of an eventual contact with ETI, Uchoa saw a tremendous flash described as like a magnesium flash. Mr. Wilson himself received a tremendous thump on his back [27]. Uchoa states he himself had contact with an entity called Yogarin and commandants named Yashamil and Zyaish [28]. This contact happened telepathically and even physically. Uchoa was told by the ETI that they came from another galaxy and traveled by space through other dimensions, faster than the light velocity limits in our tridimensional dimension [29]. Uchoa was recognized as a serious parapsychologist and researcher of paranormal phenomena, with a vast knowledge of Theosophy and especially Ufology. For two decades, he organized and coordinated UFO research expeditions. Gen. Uchoa wrote several books about these events and presented them as empirical evidence with theoretical analysis which resulted from such experiences. In Brasilia, the city where he lived during his active years of Ufology research, he founded and was President of "Uniao Pioneira de Integração Social", a well-known University in Brasilia. He also founded the Universal Morya Association and the "Centro de Estudos Ufologicos" [30]. The Brazilian media kindly named him the "General of the Stars". We concluded that this case met all the six subjective criteria and four objective criteria. Witnesses: several witnesses affirmed having seen a UFO and having encounters with ETI. They were identified in the reference books. Paranormality was considered due to several phenomena from a young age including materializations of entities, transport of objects [31] and his cures of people with diseases as the case of a woman with Chagas disease [32]. Pictures taken by different people including an official from Ministerio do Interior of Brazil [33], which we considered physical evidence. Predicted contact was considered [34]. Score: 10.

3.3.2. Second case: R-Gonzalez (Peru)

Ricardo González (born in Lima, 1974) is a renowned Peruvian researcher and writer about extraterrestrial life, lost civilizations and new consciousness. He was able to prove his link with the extraterrestrials by inviting journalists and researchers to participate in UFO sightings previously scheduled. Everything started when he was very young. First with sightings and lights that he had observed on the outskirts of the city of Lima, Peru in the area "Sierra de Chosica". In 1988 as a 13-14 year old boy, he observed in broad daylight a bright luminous object moving without emitting any noise over the city and in the direction of the ocean. Then throughout that year, the media spoke of an intense wave of UFO observations in Peru. The big event happened 5 years later in 1993. In his words: "I was studying and for a moment I closed my notebooks to relax and take a break. At that moment I heard a voice in my head; I was not hallucinating, it was not a delirium, I did not fall asleep! I heard a very clear voice, it was the voice of a man with a neutral accent that said something like - "Do not stop looking, we are extraterrestrial beings entering into communication with you. You will live a preparation so that later on you can meet us". According to Gonzales the first time he saw one of these extraterrestrial beings was on August 30th, 1997 in the Chilca desert. His account: "I was invited to have contact with these beings through telepathic communication. I was accompanied by 2 other friends that were school classmates at the time. When we arrived at the desert these objects appeared, there were lights not only above our camp but also almost at ground level. They were throwing flashes and then there was a very loud noise, a metallic sound arose, as if it were a metallic buzz that first made "plank, plank" and it remained constant. All of the sudden a very tall male silhouette appeared in the middle of the night. He approached me, I got very nervous, I tried to get closer to have communication and I said: "This can not be true". Suddenly the male silhouette lit up from the bottom up with a ring of light. He was illuminated intensely, it was clearly a man with Nordic features. He was about 25-30 meters away. He was almost 3 meters tall, so I was not looking at a normal person. He was dressed in a silver looking jumpsuit; I'm not sure, it was my perception. He illuminated himself with that ring of light that covered his entire body like a second skin, only leaving his hands and face uncovered. He introduced himself with the name of "Antarel". In another experience in 2021 with Antarel, Gonzalez got into the spacecraft. According to his account: "In that same desert I was taken through a solid beam of light that left me weightless. I went inside an object that was hidden above a low cloud mattress and inside that object I interviewed these beings. Antarel himself reappeared in this new experience in 2001. I was with them for several hours; however, little time had passed on my watch, about 1 hour and 20 minutes or so". Gonzalez also had encounters with intraterrestrial beings on several occasions [35]. Antarel who was the main interlocutor in this experience, claims to come from the triple star system of Alpha Centauri constellation. In his last communications, González shared his incredible experiences with the Apunians, extraterrestrial beings that come from the future with a

powerful message. "The messages of the ETI are very precise and they have the elements to verify them. There is a hopeful future, but some old structures have to be transformed. What I would say to people is not to be afraid because fear is the antithesis of love. Extraterrestrials may support us but they will never solve our problems" [36]. In the most recent message, Gonzalez affirms that mankind will be prepared to abandon the Earth and search for a new home in space. Those astronauts will travel to the region of Alpha Centauri in the future and their descendants will become the ETI that today visit us [37]. We concluded that this case met all the six subjective criteria and four objective criteria: Witnesses: several named witnesses affirmed having seen UFOs and having encounters with ETI, as for example, the American journalist Paola Harris [38] and the political scientist Dr. Michael Salla, PhD [39]. Paranormality was considered due to telepathy between the group confirming the predicted contact. Physical evidence was considered by pictures taken by different people in different places of contact as shown in some books [40]. Predicted contact was considered because of the seven occasions where several people including journalists were advised prior to the sighting [41]. On September 28th, 2019, in the Atacama Desert, Chile, 340 people from around 24 countries, observed an anomalous light over their camp, at the exact time previously established by a telepathic contact with González [42]. Score: 10.

3.4. Information from the authentic CE5thK cases

Table 5 Descriptive data from 'contactees' in the CE5thK of high probability of being authentic in the Epimetheus Project and compared with Final Contact Project

General data of authentic 'contactees'	Subcategory	Epimetheus Project (2022)	Final Contact Project (2016)	Total
Sex		n=14 ^a	n=27 ^a	n=41
	Male	14 (100%)	25 (92.6%)	39 (95.12%)
	Female	0 (0%)	2 (7.4%)	2 (4.88%)
Mean of age of the first encounter (years SEM)		n= 12 ^b	n=27	P=0.298
		27.83±4.35	33.74±3.19	
Age group of first event		n=12 ^b	n=27	n=39
	Children/adolescent (until 19 y)	4 (33.3%)	6 (22.2%)	10 (25.54%)
	Young adult (20-40y)	6 (50.0%)	9 (33.3%)	15 (38.46%)
	Middle adult (41-64)	2 (16.67%)	12 (44.5%)	14 (35.89%)
		n=13	n=25	N=38
Physical description of spacecraft	Yes	12 (92.31%)	25 (100.0%)	37 (97.37%)
	No	1 (7.69%)	0 (4.0%)	1 (2.63%)
Physical description of ETI		n=13	n=25	N=38
	Yes	12 (92.31%)	24 (96.0%)	36 (94.74%)
	No	1 (7.69%)	1 (4.0%)	2 (5.26%)
Telepathic manifestation		n=13	n=25	n=38
	Yes	11 (84.61%)	24 (96.0%)	35 (92.11%)
	No	2 (15.39%)	1 (4.0%)	3 (7.89%)
Number of encounters		n=13	n=25	n=38
	Once	0 (0%)	4 (16.0%)	4 (10.53%)
	Two	2 (15.39%)	1 (4.0%)	3 (7.89%)
	Three or more times	11 (84.61%)	20 (80.0%)	31 (81.58%)

Continent of origin		n=13	n=25	n=38
	South America	10 (76.93%)	15 (60.0%)	25 (65.79%)
	North America	1 (7.69%)	4 (16.0%)	5 (13.16%)
	Central America	1 (7.69%)	0 (0%)	1 (2.63%)
	Europe	0 (0%)	4 (16.0%)	4 (10.53%)
	Asia	0 (0%)	1 (4%)	1 (2.63%)
	Africa	1 (7.69%)	1 (4%)	2 (5.26%)
Immigrant		n=14	n=27	n=41
	Yes	4 (28.57%)	11 (40.7%)	15 (36.59%)
	No	10 (71.43%)	16 (59.3%)	26 (63.41%)
Number of researchers by case		n=13	n=25	n=38
	Two	9 (69.23%)	11 (44%)	20 (52.63%)
	Three or more	4 (30.77%)	14 (56.0%)	18 (47.37%)

^a In the EP in one case of CE5thK there was two 'contactees' and in the FCP 2 cases of CE5thK there were 2 'contactees'.

^b In 2 cases there was no information about the age of first contact.

As we found some CE5thK cases with high probability of being authentic, our second objective was the characterization and analysis of information from them in the same way as in the FCP. In one case there were two witnesses of the contact phenomenon and in one of these cases the information regarding the sex of all the witnesses was absent. So from 14 authentic 'contactees', there was total predominance of men compared with women (14 vs. 0 respectively) similar to the FCP. In addition, when we analyzed the rate of authentic 'contactees' by sex in the entire series from both studies (n=138) we found that the rate of authentic 'contactee' men was significantly higher than women (34.8% vs. 6.9%, p=0.002).

The mean age of first encounter was not different between FCP and EP (p=0.298). The first contact happened from adolescence to middle adulthood. The youngest age was 11 y and the oldest 60 y. The CE5thK phenomena is worldwide, with cases originating on several continents, though logically most of these we found locally mainly in South America (76.93%). The rate of immigrants was 28.57% (Table 5). When compared to the findings of the FCP, we observed the same trends in these variables.

As in the FCP we assumed that the authentic 'contactees' did not have substantial knowledge about the other 'contactees' in the series, because of geographical distances, language differences and some cases not being contemporaries. This assumption permitted us to do additional tests in order to search for consistency among them or to find any possible interrelations among them. The physical description of ETI (92.31%) or the physical description of a spacecraft was present in 12 of 13 cases (92.31%), and a telepathic manifestation (84.62%) was present in most of the cases. The number of encounters of two or more times was present in 100.0% of cases. Again when compared to the findings of the FCP we observed the same trends in these variables. (Table 5).

As observed in the FCP, the communication in all the authentic cases were bidirectional and happened by oral, mental or by other means (letter and telephone calls in one case). The 'contactee' or 'contactees' were conscious in the experience when the dialogue happened. With respect to the questions, this differed between the witnesses, the context of experience of 'contactee', and the nature and origin of ETI. In general, the questions were more frequent from the human beings. The answers resulted in a volume of information in fields of history, scientific theories, religion and philosophy. Following the same trends in the FCP, the information indicated that the origin of ETI were different, including different planets or satellites from our Solar System, other constellations in our galaxy, other galaxies, other dimensions, and some of unknown origin. In some cases, ETI affirmed that they originated from more than one location (Table 6). The ETI informed the 'contactees' that their motivations for visiting Earth were study or exploration missions, giving alerts to humankind such as about nuclear hazards, and awakening consciousness, as presented in Table 6. The majority of these cases were given information of more than one motivation at the same time.

Specific information passed from ETI with substantial concordance observed in the FCP among the authentic ‘contactees’ included “vegetarianism as dietetic pattern recommended” (vegetarianism), “critics-of-capitalism or money-based system” (money-critics), “reincarnation as a real and existent phenomenon” (“reincarnation”) and “assurance of the presence of ETI living among us” (ETI among us). In the EP, we also observed the same trends (Table 6). “Vegetarianism” was found to be in six (75%) out of 8 authentic CE5thK cases with available information. On the contrary, in two cases, consumption of fish or meat was permitted. “Capitalism-Money-critics” was present in all five cases (100%) with information available. No ‘contactee’ communication with ETI recommended or justified this economic model. “Reincarnation” as a real and existent phenomenon was present in all seven cases (100%) with available information. None of the cases had any information denying this phenomenon. The assurance of the presence of ETI living among us was found in all eight cases (100%) with available information. In none of these cases was it was denied. Table 6.

Table 6 Concordant Information received by ‘contactees’ from ETI in the CE5thK of high probability of being authentic in the Epimetheus Project and compared with Final Contact Project

Information received from ETI	Subcategory	Epimetheus Project (2022)	Final Contact Project (2016)	Total
Origin of ETI ^a		n=13	n=25	n=28
	Planets in Solar System	7 (53.85%)	10 (40%)	17 (60.71%)
	Constellation of our galaxy	4 (30.77%)	8 (32%)	12 (42.86%)
	Unknown planet	1 (7.69%)	9 (36%)	10 (35.71%)
	Other galaxy or dimension	3 (23.08%)	10 (40%)	13 (46.435)
	Not informed	2 (15.38%)	3 (12%)	5 (17.86%)
Motivations of visiting Earth ^b		n=13	n=25	n=38
	Study or exploration mission	7 (53.85%)	17 (68%)	24 (63.16%)
	Alert to mankind	11 (84.62%)	19 (76%)	30 (78.95%)
	Nuclear hazard	9 (69.23%)	15 (60.0%)	24 (63.16%)
	Awakening consciousness	12 (92.31%)	19 (76.0%)	31 (81.58%)
	Not informed	0 (0%)	2 (8.0%)	2 (5.26%)
Vegetarianism as pattern recommended		n=8 ^c	n=19 ^c	n=27
	Yes	6 (75%)	16 (84.2%)	22 (81.48%)
	Consumption of meat permitted	1 (12.5%0	1 (5.3%)	2 (7.41%)
	Consumption of fish permitted	1 (12.5%)	2 (10.5%)	3 (11.11%)
Critics of capitalism or money-based system		n= 5 ^c	n=18 ^c	n=23
	Yes	5 (100%)	18 (100%)	23 (100%)
	No	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Reincarnation as real phenomenon		n=7 ^c	n=12 ^c	n=19
	Yes	7 (100%)	12 (100%)	19 (100%)
	No	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Presence of ETI among us		n=8 ^c	n= 15 ^c	n=23
	Yes	8 (100%)	15 (100%)	23 (100%0
	No	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

^a In each CE5thK ETI affirmed to have different origins; ^b In each CE5thK ETI affirmed to have different motivations; ^c In spite of the total number of authentic ‘contactees’ being higher; in these variables the information was not available for all.

We also decided to analyze original information not published from the FCP related to different topics that did not have substantial concordance but its presence in some cases is of great interest. In addition, we compared and summed this information with the EP. (Table 7). The following findings were made from the summed results of both FCP and EP studies. In the rest of the cases where the particular subject was not mentioned, neither was it denied or contradicted. It was observed that abduction phenomena (CE4) was experienced by 11 'contactees' in both studies (28.95% out 38 cases). In other words, in more than one quarter of the authentic 'contactees' determined to be authentic, the experience of CE5thK was preceded by a CE4. The reports of the 'contactees' having physically traveled inside a spacecraft was present in 30 (78.95%) cases, which is high. There were 21 reports of the presence of a 'fine screen television device' inside the spacecraft in both studies (55.26%). Regarding this point we must clarify that not all 'contactees' had the opportunity to enter into spacecraft.

Table 7 Novel technical and scientific information received by 'contactees' from ETI in CE5thK cases of high probability of being authentic in the Epimetheus Project and in the Final Contact Project

Novel Knowledge specific points	Subcategory	Epimetheus Project n=13 (% of total)	Final Contact Project n=25 (% of total)	Total (n=38)
Abduction phenomenon as part of 'contactee' experience	Yes	6 (46.15%)	5 (20.0%)	11 (28.95%)
	No	7 (53.85%)	20 (80%)	27 (71.05%)
Physical travel in a spacecraft by 'contactee'	Yes	9 (69.23%)	21 (84.0%)	30 (78.95%)
	No	4 (30.77%)	4 (16.0%)	8 (21.05%)
Presence of 'fine screen television device' inside the spacecraft ^a	Yes	5 (38.46%)	16 (64%)	21 (55.26%)
	Neither stated or denied	8 (61.54%)	9 (36%)	17 (44.74%)
Existence of intraterrestrial beings or undersea bases confirmed	Yes	8 (61.54%)	7 (28%)	15 (39.47%)
	Neither stated or denied	5 (38.46%)	18 (72%)	23 (60.53%)
Existence of civilizations unknown in the past of mankind confirmed	Yes	4 (30.77%)	13 (52%)	17 (44.74%)
	Neither stated or denied	9 (69.23%)	12 (48%)	21(55.26%)
Known historical characters cited by ETI	Yes	7 (53.85%)	12(48%)	19 (50%)
	Neither stated or denied	6 (46.15%)	13(52%)	19 (50%)
Lifespans of ETI longer than human beings confirmed	Yes	5 (38.46%)	7 (28%)	12 (31.58%)
	Neither stated or denied	8 (61.54%)	18 (72%)	26 (68.42%)
Domain of Artificial insemination by ETI	Yes	1 (7.69%)	5 (20%)	6 (15.79%)
	Neither stated or denied	12 (92.31%)	0 (80%)	32 (84.21%)
Possibility of human body duplicity or cloning	Yes	3 (23.08%)	2 (8%)	5 (13.16%)
	Neither stated or denied	10 (76.92%)	23 (92%)	33 (86.84%)
Risk overpopulation on the Earth/ Birth control recommended	Yes	1 (7.69%)	6 (24%)	7 (18.42%)
	Neither stated or denied	12 (92.31%)	19 (76%)	31 (81.58%)
	Yes	8 (61.54%)	7 (28%)	15 (39.47%)

Eventual rescue of human beings in the case of humanity’s extinction	Neither stated or denied	5 (38.46%)	18 (72%)	23 (60.53%)
Presence of human beings living on other planets	Yes	6 (46.15%)	4 (16.0%)	10 (26.32%)
	Neither stated or denied	7 (53.85%)	21(84.0%)	28 (73.68%)
Parallel worlds or dimensions as real phenomena	Yes	9 (69.23%)	9 (36%)	18 (47.37%)
	Neither stated or denied	4 (30.77%)	16 (64%)	20 (52.63%)
‘Stargate’ or dimensional gate as real phenomena	Yes	8 (61.54%)	6 (24%)	14 (36.84%)
	Neither stated or denied	5 (38.46%)	19 (76%)	24 (63.16%)
Time travel as real phenomena	Yes	7 (53.85%)	5(20%)	12 (31.58%)
	Neither stated or denied	6 (46.15%)	20(80%)	26 (68.42%)

^a Not all ‘contactees’ entered inside of a spacecraft. In the Epimetheus Project there were 5 and in the FCP there were 20 ‘contactees’ that experienced it.

Reports of the existence of intraterrestrial beings (or intraterrestrial /undersea bases) was stated by 15 (39.47%) ‘contactees’ from both studies. The existence of civilizations unknown in mankind’s past was reported by 17 (44.74%) ‘contactees’ deemed authentic. Known historical characters cited by ETI were reported in 19 (50%) of the cases deemed authentic.

*Y-axis: values correspond to the percentage of total sample of CE5thK of high probability to be authentic from both studies.

Figure 4 Characteristics and information reported highly concordant in CE5thK cases of high probability to be authentic from the Final Contact Project and the Epimetheus Project(n=38)*

The information of the lifespans of ETI being longer than human beings was stated by 12 (31.58%) of the authentic ‘contactees’. The possibility of human body duplication or cloning was reported by five (13.16%) authentic ‘contactees’. The topic of artificial insemination by ETI was reported in six cases (15.79%). Risk of overpopulation on the Earth or birth control recommendations was reported in seven cases (18.42%). The possibility of eventual rescue of human beings in the case of humanity’s extinction was passed onto the ‘contactee’ in 15 cases (39.47%). The information about presence of human beings living on other planets was reported in 10 cases (26.325%).

The information about ‘parallel worlds or dimensions as real phenomena’ was reported in 18 authentic cases (47.37%) from both studies. The information of ‘stargate or dimensional gate as real phenomena’ was reported by 14 authentic ‘contactees’ (36.84%). The information about the ‘time travel as real phenomena’ was reported in 12 (31.58%) ‘contactee’ cases deemed authentic.

In addition, with the characteristics and specific information reported more concordant from both studies, we created a graphic (Figure 4) showing the 12 characteristics most frequent in the CE5th of high probability of being authentic. They included: masculine sex, spacecraft description, ETI description, physical travel in a spacecraft, three or more encounters with ETI, telepathic manifestation, motivation of awakening consciousness, motivation of alert to mankind, vegetarianism as dietetic pattern recommended, critics to capitalism or money based-system, reincarnation as real phenomena, and presence of ETI among us.

4. Discussion

In the EP study, we investigated a new series of ‘contactees’ from alleged CE5thK cases, and used the twelve criteria method from the prior FCP to determine authenticity. We found evidence to support that some new cases of alleged CE5thK had a high probability to be truly advanced contact of ETI with human beings on Earth. Compared with the FCP, the EP rate of authentic ‘contactees’ was significantly lower. In addition, we show original information from both studies passed from ETI not shown before, with amazing potential for our society in different fields of knowledge.

The fact that a new trained team of researchers carried out this work builds the possibility that other similar studies using the same method could be carried out on different continents, and eventually further confirm the results of these studies.

4.1. Categories of alleged ‘contactees’

The percentage of cases considered as “low probability to be authentic” was significantly higher in the more recent EP study than the rate observed in the FCP. In both the FCP and EP, we considered this category as not real, i.e. false.

We found this result was associated with some variables suggesting this series of cases is more modern. The series of the EP had more cases with the main information coming primarily from virtual sources. Also, the rate of ‘contactees’ still being alive was logically higher in the more recent EP, and the mean year of publication more recent. All three significant differences support that cases in the EP were more modern compared to the FCP. As the rate of false ‘contactees’ (low probability to be authentic) was higher in the EP we can hypothesize that modern communications with an increasing number of detailed ETI stories being circulated makes it easier for more people to publicly assert fabricated ETI contact histories without evidence of authenticity. The openness and higher acceptance of Ufology is clearly represented by different programs and channels like the History Channel. Also, the acceptance of some governments of the UFO phenomena has caused them to create special agencies to study UFOs, such as Uruguay, France, Peru, Chile and recently the United States. It is probable that the ease of modern communications could lead to freeing the ego of more people searching for fame and notoriety. Among them, there are individuals very well known in the local and international circles of Ufology and spiritualism. As commented on in the FCP, there may be different explanations of what was happening in these fabricated or otherwise false cases. We think that some of the mechanisms by skeptics to explain the abductions (CE4) as non-extraterrestrial phenomenon could be at work here. Some possibilities are hoaxes, delusion or psychosis enhanced imagery [43] due to temporal lobe liability that within specific contexts can facilitate the creation of memories [44], false memory syndrome [45] or fantasy [46]. Our determination for these cases is that advanced contact is probably not true. The importance of these findings of false ‘contactees’ affirming having had a true CE5thK is in the fact that these people lead a great number of followers and readers into disinformation and lead to an eventual debunking of the real possibility of true CE5thK, which indeed probably happens, as we have shown in both studies.

We found that the rate of ‘contactees’ determined to have a high probability of being authentic was significantly lower in this EP study compared to the FCP, approximately one-fifth of the EP total cases compared to one third of the FCP total cases. We can speculate that if the same trend continues into the future, the rate of authentic ‘contactees’ found in a new series of cases of alleged ‘contactees’ analyzed under the twelve criteria method will be found to be lower, or perhaps even approach zero.

In this EP study, we found the first case in the “Inconclusive Evidence” category. We had not found a single such case in this category in the FCP. This category was created when a case apparently seemed authentic but lacked any objective criteria which would give any proof of authenticity.

It is important to point out that in this EP study, the score in one case of low probability (StaRo) was six, the same score that the one case of Inconclusive Evidence received (ang-L). By definition, the category “Evidence Inconclusive” must have all six subjective and none of the objective criteria. In the case of low probability, the case does not have all the six subjective criteria, independent of objective criteria. In the case of low probability mentioned (StaRo), it had four

subjective criteria and two objective criteria. In theory, one case of low probability could score a higher value than a case of Inconclusive Evidence or High Probability, but without meeting all subjective criteria.

In the EP study, we considered the cases of high probability technically authentic. It is important to point out that as in the earlier FCP study, we observed a phenomenon that we called "contamination", where in true advanced contact, some information reported by the authentic 'contactee' could not be absolutely precise and exact due to difficulty in recalling details of the experience, for example, the exact hour and date of contact experience. The matter in discussion here is restricted to the possibility of advanced contact with ETI at least one time in any case. Additionally, a phenomenon similar but in opposite sense would be perceived in the group "low probability" that we called "reverse contamination" when valid or correct information from abilities or knowledge from non-authentic (false) 'contactees' incorporated publicly published information from real advanced ETI 'contactees' with the aim of giving more credibility to their false accounts.

From 2016 until now, in our identification of authentic 'contactees', we found some with more scoring in objective criteria scores of 10 or more, which we labeled as 'super-contactees' meaning those with more hard evidence [47]. From the four cases described with more details in both FCP and EP studies, three were considered 'super-contactees'. The 'contactee' Sixto Paz from the RAMA case had several times experiences of predicted contact of UFO phenomenon including journalist from different countries in 1989. The 'contactee' Donato Cervantes in the 'DCC' case from the FCP had the highest score of 12, in a way a 'perfect score' [16]. He had evidence of amazing healing by ETI of infected arm (gangrene) that had indication of amputation by the risk of sepsis. There were clinical records and several witnesses confirming different paranormal phenomena including telepathy and special abilities of the healed arm [48, 49].

4.2. Gender

As carried out in the FCP, the deeper analysis of characteristics and information received in the authentic CE5thK cases revealed interesting information of technical, biological, social, and philosophical nature. The rate of authentic 'contactees' in the entire series from both studies, was significantly higher in men than women (34.82% vs. 7.69%). In other words, one of 3 male alleged 'contactees', and one of 14 alleged female 'contactees' were determined to be authentic, a rate nearly 5 times higher for males than females. In addition, in the group of 'contactees' deemed authentic, there was a predominance of men in both studies, at a ratio of 20 to 1 (95.12 vs. 4.88%). All this leads to several speculations. Do the men have structural characteristics or psychic abilities which better prepare them for an eventual contact? Are men involved in activities more prone to contact? Is the reason males are more likely to experience advanced contact related to our historically male-dominated society? Until what point the book 'Men are from Mars, Women are from Venus' could be a metaphor? [50].

4.3. Spacecraft and ET Beings

In the earlier FCP study, a physical description of spacecraft and of ETI was present in 25 (100%) and 24 (96%) respectively of cases. The later EP study also had a description of a spacecraft and of ETI in 12 of 13 cases (92.31%), following the same trend in the FCP. Both studies described grey, nordic, and dark-skinned human types. Both studies described the shape of the spacecraft as circular, oval, cylindrical, or a saucer shaped. Previously, extensive literature just reported the variability in morphology of spacecraft or ETI [51].

4.4. First and Repeated Contact

As in the FCP, the EP showed that first contact could occur starting from infancy all the way to middle adulthood. In 81.58% of cases from both studies, the contact phenomenon repeated three or more times. This last finding could mean a kind of preferential relationship is built with an authentic 'contactee'. We can find a similarity with the idea supported by Shettleworth [52] that showed that researchers of animals applying the sensitization that is a non-associative learning process in which repeated administrations of a stimulus results in the progressive amplification of a response. We can speculate that depending on the kind of ETI that makes the contact, repeated encounters could be necessary in order to get determined answers or behaviors from human beings.

4.5. Geographical Distribution and Immigrants

In spite of these authentic CE5thK cases being considered a worldwide phenomenon, we found again in the EP study that there was predominance of South American authentic 'contactees'. This would be most likely explained by the South American location of the project and higher availability of South America information sources. However, we cannot discard other reasons such as richness in natural resources or presence of historic and archaeological sites located on this continent. The relatively high rate of immigrants (36.59%) in authentic CE5thK cases from both studies compared

with the general population (3.1% according to a 2008 UN study [53] leads to speculation that those experimenting with an inter-cultural situation are more probable to have an advanced contact with ETI.

4.6. Origins and Motivations of ETI

Confirming the findings in the FCP, in this EP study we observed that according to the information given by the ETI, there are different kinds of civilizations with several places of origin, even planets or satellites within our Solar System. Furthermore, the motivations of the different ETIs coming to the Earth were diverse. All these observations could explain the different patterns of physical appearance, shapes of spacecraft, and behaviors observed in the reported advanced contact with ETI [54]. Freitas affirmed that the assertion that ETI do not exist rests upon an unproven and untenable presumption: that ETI are currently not present in the Solar System [11]. The recent discovery of phosphine on Venus generated a buzz that the planet, often succinctly touted as a “hellscape,” could somehow harbor life within its acidic clouds [55]. In 2017, the first interstellar object was discovered in the solar system, ‘Oumuamua’ (1I/2017 U1). Loeb and Bialy published a paper arguing that ‘Oumuamua had been nothing less than humanity’s first contact with an artifact of extraterrestrial intelligence [56]. They even proposed that ‘Oumuamua’ may be a fully operational probe sent intentionally to Earth’s vicinity by an alien civilization [57]. The classic observational status of the Solar System is insufficient to support the assumption that ETI are not here. Most advanced civilizations also might be either invisible or unrecognizable using current human observational methods, so millions of advanced societies may exist and still not be directly detectable by us. Baum suggests that ETI intentionally hide from us, which would cause these objects to become difficult to locate and practically invisible. They could have the capability of hiding from us given the likelihood of their superior technology. There are many ways that ETI could remain undetected by us if they chooses to do so [58]. In this respect, Ball suggests that extraterrestrial intelligent life may be almost ubiquitous, and that the apparent failure of such life to interact with us may be understood in terms of the hypothesis that they have set us aside as part of a wilderness area or zoo (the “Zoo Hypothesis”) [59]. In addition, there is the conjectured possibility of making use of the additional dimensionalities of superstring and M-brane theory to transfer into adjacent universes where the speed of light limit may be quite different, and then reentering our universe at the desired location [60].

4.7. Concordant Specific Information about Advanced Technology and Philosophies

In the EP, as in the FCP, when we analyzed the information received by ‘contactees’ that showed strong concordance among authentic ‘contactees’ in some specific variables, we observed the same trends. With respect to the scientific validity of some specific information such as “telepathy”, “vegetarianism”, “money-critics” and “reincarnation”, new discoveries are confirming this. Telepathy is now a recognized phenomenon studied by several researchers [61, 62]. Researchers from the University of Washington have recently reported an interesting experiment in which they copied electrical signals from one person imagining a motor action and transmitted them to another person who effectively executed the imagined movement. They used an electroencephalogram-recording module and the receiver to transmit the electrical signal to a transcranial magnetic stimulation unit and a computer connected to TMS machine [63, 64]. It is interesting that in the 1978 ‘Karran case’ from the FCP, the authentic ‘contactees’ described a device for thought transmission connected in the head of ‘contactees’ in order to communicate with ETI [65].

Vegetarianism is clearly more beneficial than an occidental or conventional diet with respect to prevention and treatment of chronic diseases of high morbidity and mortality such as diabetes mellitus [66], cardiovascular diseases [67, 68], cancer [69] and fatal pandemics such as Covid-19 [70, 71]. Recently, it was shown that longevity in vegetarians is higher than omnivorous subjects [72, 73]. The consumption of fish can also offer protection and lower mortality from cardiovascular disease [74, 75]. In addition, a plant-based diet was recognized by an International Commission of experts as an ideal diet for the planet [76]. We propose that the “Homo-vegetarian” will be the next evolutionary step for humanity, based on physiological, biochemical and genetic changes observed in long-lived vegetarian subjects [77]. In addition, in the case of 7.4% of cases where the ETI stated meat consumption is permitted, one could speculate that manufactured meat could be an alternative. Novel alternatives to meat (plant- or cell-based) may provide a similar sensorial experience to traditional meat, but with a potentially smaller environmental impact [78]. It could be a cultured meat or cell meat that at present our technology is producing and has hybrid properties from animal and vegetal characteristics. These are produced from animal cells but without the necessity of sacrificing animals, and avoid the risk of contamination [79]. The VlaK case from the FCP, described an ETI offering artificial meat to a woman who just arrived on his planet [80].

Great thinkers and philosophers critical of capitalism or money-based systems have existed for several centuries [81]. The recent economic crisis that is affecting America and Europe mainly from 2008 could reflect again the reality of a system destined to implode [82]. We made criticisms and proposed an alternative to it [83]. The present Ukraine War confronting Russia against NATO is supported mainly by the United States, and involves two nuclear powers with capitalist and imperialist economic models resulting in a real threat of extinction of humanity. The result of this system

appears destined to destruction [84]. Some scientists, such as Paul Poast [85], suggest the Ukraine War is the beginning of World War III.

Reincarnation and the related concept of life after death is a scientific matter studied by several researchers that believe both are indeed real phenomenon [86-88]. In the VlaK case cited above, the 'contactee' with ETI from Apu planet (Alfa Centauro) describes ways how the reincarnation process could happen [89]. In addition, others 'contactees' stated that previous characters known in our history have been reincarnated [80, 90]. We also show that in the three variables of vegetarianism as dietetic pattern recommended, critics of capitalism or money-based system, and reincarnation belief as real phenomenon, many people from different cultures on Earth have different beliefs than most of extraterrestrial civilizations.

4.8. ETIs Among Us

The affirmation that ETI are among us is amazing information. This could lead us to believe that some of these ETI look very much like us. Indeed, the description of several types of ETI from authentic 'contactees' describe Nordic, Caucasian and brown skinned beings. In addition, they could have developed a technology or science able to transform themselves or metamorphize into the appearance of a human being, much like certain animals here on the Earth, such as octopuses or chameleons. In addition, we could speculate that some contemporary characters might be suspected to be ETI, such as Ernesto 'Che' Guevara, Luis Soto Romero, Eduard Snowden, or Julian Assange [91]. All were figures against the dominant system and showed much decision and courage. Exactly how ETI could proceed to carry out abducting and changing people's bodies, reincarnating, or influencing their minds, is beyond the scope of our discussion.

4.9. The Typical Experience

The last characteristics and information from authentic CE5thK cases allow us to give a picture of the typical experience of an authentic CE5thK. This includes a 'contactee' of male sex, a description of ETI, description of spacecraft, travel into the spacecraft, telepathic manifestation and several encounters. The motivations of ETI have been given as further awakening the human consciousness, alerts to humankind, information recommending vegetarianism, criticism of capitalism or money-based systems, confirming that reincarnation is a real phenomenon, and that ETI are present in our society.

4.10. Novel Specific Information in Some Authentic Cases from both studies

This paper has become a hybrid study combining data and discussion from both the FCP and EP studies. When we analyzed novel information from the FCP and EP, there was not necessarily substantial concordance from all 'contactees' in the 38 CE5thK cases with a high probability of being authentic. But we did observe some very interesting findings.

The phenomena of abduction (CE4) as part of a contactee's experience was found in 28.95% of all authentic 'contactees' cases. This suggests that the categorization of CE4^h and CE5thK is more academic than real. Our findings also suggest that in some cases, abduction could be an initial phase of a CE5thK. Abduction is indeed a subject studied in scientific literature, but most of these studies attempt to explain away the experience as resulting from causes other than real extraterrestrial contact [14]. On the other hand, in a recent study of 3,256 people around the world on self-reported various other forms of contact experience (near-death experiences, out-of-body experience, mystical meditation travel, channeling, remote viewing) along with ETI associated with UFOs, the researchers found that the alleged 'contactees' reported spiritual experiences, while 'abductees' reported physical experiences. That work differs from ours because the definition of contact is not equivalent, and it does not use any validation criterion to determine if a case is probably authentic [92].

In both the FCP and EP study, 78.95% of authentic 'contactees' reported physically traveling in the spacecraft. This percentage is high considering that mainstream science denies extraterrestrial contact with human beings happens. It also implies that the phenomena of CE5thK is a physical experience. In some cases, the travel was over the Earth [93]. In others, the travel was further out from the Earth, as with Magocsi [94] and Sixto Paz [95], who stated they had traveled to a city on Ganymede, Jupiter's satellite. It also was reported that in 55.26% of all authentic cases in the FCP and EP, the 'contactees' observed a fine screen inside the spacecraft that showed pictures of real-time moments or in some cases, pictures from the past. It is interesting that the description of this screen in cases from the 1960's, when televisions were just beginning to be produced and only black and white images were possible, the Vitko Novi 'contactee' case for example (VlaK case in the FCP), Vitko's description was similar to a modern LCD with color and 3-D television. Figure 5.

Figure 5 “Exceso” daily reporting the experience of contact with extraterrestrial beings of the ‘contactee’ Vlado Kapetamovich (VlaK case) in Huallanca, Peru, October 28th, 1973.

In 39.47% of the authentic ‘contactee’ cases in both studies, the ‘contactee’ was told of the existence of intraterrestrial beings, and/or extraterrestrial underground bases or undersea bases. In some cases including R Gonzales, the ‘contactee’ reported having had physical encounters with intraterrestrial beings. Sixto Paz reported visiting an undersea base [96]. Likewise in another case, ‘DCC’ from FCP study, a cure of an earlier amputation of part of his fingers happened in a similar undersea base in northern Peru, according to the account of the ‘contactee’ [48].

4.11. Historical Information

Existence of unknown civilizations in humanity’s past was spoken of by 44.74% of authentic ‘contactees’ in both studies. There is archeological and historical evidence suggesting the possibility that Earth was visited in ancient times by ETI. Ancient extraterrestrial theorists believe that thousands of years ago, ETI landed on Earth where they were hailed as gods and helped shape human civilization [10, 97]. Recently scientists studying the Anthropocene—the proposed epoch of Earth’s geologic history in which humanity’s activities dominate the globe—proposed that industrially induced climate change resembles conditions seen in past periods of rapid temperature rise. “These ‘hyperthermals’ are the thermal-maximum events of prehistory. An example of such a hyperthermal is the Paleocene–Eocene Thermal Maximum (PETM), a 200,000-year period that occurred some 55.5 million years ago when global average temperatures rose by 5 to 8 degrees Celsius. It is during this period that the Silurian Hypothesis is proposed. Basically, it states that human beings might not be the first intelligent life forms to have evolved on this planet, and that if there really were precursors some 100 million years ago, virtually all signs of them would have been lost by now [98]. In our studies, several authentic ‘contactees’ confirmed the existence of Atlantis, Lemuria, Mu and other very ancient civilizations.

In 50% of all cases of authentic ‘contactees,’ known historical characters were cited by ETI. In most of these cases, the citation affirmed that they influenced these characters. Some known historical characters were cited by some authentic ‘contactees’ from the 1960’s as being influenced by ETI. These include Emanuel Swedenborg, Nikola Tesla, Helena Blavatsky, Pd. D Outpensky [99], Protagoras, Jesus of Nazareth, Francisco Petrarca, Leonardo da Vinci, Joan of Arc, Christopher Columbus, Martin Luther, Abraham Lincoln, Friederich Hegel, Karl Marx [80], Giordano Bruno [89], and Pierre and Marie Curie [100]. Based on these names, we could hypothesize the possibility that some prophets, founders of great religions, and other significant historical persons might have also been in contact with ETI.

4.12. Biological Nature Information

With respect to biological information, in 31.58% of cases of authentic ‘contactees’ cases from both studies, it was relayed that the lifespan of an ETI is much longer than human beings. It is known that life expectancy for our modern civilization is higher than in the past due advances in medicine and public health. In Ancient Roman times lifespans averaged 30 years, and is now more than 70 years in developed countries. No one foresaw that continued increase in life expectancy. It has taken our politicians and planners by surprise. Scientists are still coming to terms with the notion that aging is not fixed, that average life spans have not reached a limit [101]. From here, it could be supposed that ETI has developed technological advances in health sciences which allow a longer life. In some cases, authentic ‘contactees’ were informed that in some civilizations ETI could live for 10,000 years, as cited by Rimax [100] in his contact with ETI from Pleiades. Vitko Novi (VlaK case) stated in his contact with ETI from Apu planet, lifespans there are more than 1 million of years. In the Vitko case, the ‘contactee’ was informed that these ETI discovered technological methods of exchanging their natural blood for artificial blood, and using a species of plant produced by biotechnology with the capacity to regenerate blood cells [80].

In 15.79% of all authentic cases, the ‘contactee’ was informed that ETI use artificial insemination for ETI reproduction. It is interesting that in the case VlaK, from the FCP, which happened in the 1960’s, the ‘contactee’ received this information well ahead of our own scientific development [80]. It was a decade later on July 25, 1978, with the birth of Louise Joy Brown, that the world’s first baby to be conceived via in vitro fertilization was born at General Hospital in Manchester, England.

In five of 38 cases (13.16%), the authentic CE5thK information received suggests the possibility of human being duplication or cloning. In one case published in 1975 (On-Pate case), the ‘contactee’ saw a copy of himself [102]. It is interesting to consider that our science only recently was able to clone animals, a sheep known as Dolly in 1996. Afterwards, the idea of human cloning became a hot debated topic [103]. The first hybrid human clone was created in November 1998, by Advanced Cell Technology. It was created using somatic cell nuclear transfer. The embryo was destroyed after 12 days [104].

In seven of 38 cases (18.42%) from both studies the ‘contactee’ was informed that there is a risk of overpopulation on the Earth, or that birth control is recommended. More people means an increased demand for food, water, housing, transportation. All this contributes to ecological degradation, increased conflicts, and a higher risk of large-scale disasters like pandemics. It is important to emphasize that, for all these variables commented on above in the rest of the cases where it was not spoken of, neither was it denied. The topic was simply not touched upon during the dialogue.

With respect to the information of an eventual rescue of human beings in the case of risk of humanity’s extinction, in 15 of 38 (39.47%) of cases and in 10 of 38 (26.32%) of authentic CE5thK cases, the ‘contactees’ were informed that human beings are living on other planets. Sixto Paz [95] affirmed that several humans were transported to a place called Morlen City on Ganymedes. Obviously, we cannot discuss this last piece of information from other studies, but here we can speculate if perhaps people who disappeared in encounters with UFOs could have been transported to other planets.

4.13. Information about the Universe and Time Travel

In 18 of 38 cases (47.37%) of authentic CE5thK from both studies, the ‘contactee’ received information that parallel worlds or dimensions were real phenomena. The multiverse is a hypothetical group of multiple universes and comprise everything that exists: the entirety of space, time, matter, energy, information, and the physical laws and constants that describe them. Other terms used for the concept are "parallel universes", "other universes", "alternate universes", or "parallel worlds". In Dublin in 1952, Erwin Schrödinger gave a lecture in which he jocularly warned his audience that what he was about to say might "seem lunatic". He said that when his equations seemed to describe several different histories, these were "not alternatives, but all really happen simultaneously" [105]. This sort of duality is called "superposition". The prevailing theory in modern cosmology, getting recognition in the 1980s, suggests that such "parallel universes" may really exist—in fact, that a multitude of universes could incessantly pop out of a primordial vacuum the way ours did in the Big Bang. Our universe would be but one of many pocket universes within a wider expanse called the multiverse. In the overwhelming majority of those universes, the laws of physics might not allow the formation of matter as we know it, or of galaxies, stars, planets and life, but given the utter number of possibilities, nature would have had a good chance to get the “right” set of laws at least once and some of these other universes may be hospitable after all. [106].

In 14 of 38 authentic cases (36.84%) from both studies, the concept of a ‘stargate or dimensional gate’ was understood as a real phenomenon. A Stargate is an Einstein–Rosen bridge portal device within the Stargate fictional universe that allows practical, rapid travel between two distant locations. It was based on theoretical astrophysics, particularly that

of black holes and wormholes, a staple of science fiction, often used to create "shortcuts" through space. Although these may exist in reality, it is not widely held to be true that any such phenomenon could safely transport a human being [107] as such wormholes would most likely be created by excessive gravity (e.g., from a black hole), which would destroy any potential traveler. It is very interesting that in the RAMA case (from the FCP), which happened in 1974, he described a dimensional gate called "xendra", a space-time threshold with the same properties described decades later. Sixto Paz was informed that ETI were able to concentrate energy to dematerialize a person and project him or her to other places by altering the molecular cohesion and atomic weight. In this way the ETI were traveling by this dimensional gate to Ganymedes. In addition, he was informed that the time passed in that place would be not the same time as on the Earth [95].

Finally in 12 of 38 (31.58%) of authentic CE5thK cases from both studies, the 'contactees' received the information that time travel was a real phenomenon. Time travel defined as the movement between certain points in time, analogous to movement between different points in space by an object or a person. It has been suggested that in the future, with improved technology, we might be able to create traversable wormholes connecting distant regions of spacetime. These wormholes would allow rapid space travel and, thus, possibly, travel back in time. [108]. Many in the scientific community believe that backward time travel is highly unlikely. Any theory that would allow time travel would introduce potential problems of causality as the "grandfather paradox" [109]. Time travel to the past is theoretically possible in certain general relativity spacetime geometries that permit traveling faster than the speed of light, such as cosmic strings, traversable wormholes, and Alcubierre drives [110]. To support this, in 1948 Kurt Godel produced a solution of Einstein's gravitational field equations that described a rotating universe. In this universe, an astronaut could travel through space to reach his own past because of the way gravity affects light. The rotation of the universe would drag light around with it, enabling a material object to travel in a closed loop in space that is also a closed loop in time, without at any stage exceeding the speed of light in the immediate neighborhood of the particle. Other scenarios have been found to permit travel into the past. For example, in 1974 Frank J. Tipler calculated that a massive, infinitely long cylinder spinning on its axis at near the speed of light could let astronauts visit their own past, again by dragging light around the cylinder into a loop [111]. R Gonzales [36], among others authentic 'contactees', said that ETI that contacted him told him that they are coming from the future.

4.14. Explanatory Hypotheses of Extraterrestrial Contact Phenomena

In spite of all the information received that could have a potential impact on our society, we must consider that the information provided by authentic 'contactees' in the CE5thK from ETI might not necessarily be true or valid in part or all of the content. We could speculate that if the "Zoo Hypothesis" were correct [59] the ETI could be testing our reactions and behaviors in the face of the phenomenon. Another theory is the Interdimensional Hypothesis (IDH) proposed by several scientists, such as John Keel [112] and Jacques Valle [113]. It states that UFOs and related events involve visitations from other "realities" or "dimensions" that coexist separately alongside our own. It is not necessarily an alternative to the extraterrestrial hypothesis, since the two hypotheses are not mutually exclusive. Both could be true simultaneously. The IDH also holds that UFOs are a modern manifestation of a phenomenon that has occurred throughout recorded human history, which in prior ages were ascribed to mythological or supernatural creatures. One advantage of IDH proffered by Evans [114] is its ability to explain the apparent ability of UFOs to appear and disappear from sight and radar; this is explained as the UFO entering and leaving our dimension ("materializing" and "dematerializing"). Recently we presented the "Homeric Stage Hypothesis" [115] where the relation of ETI with human beings even in modern times would hold similar characteristics as described by Homer in his classical "Iliad" and "Odyssey". They would act as gods or semi-gods with many behavioral features of human nature. All these hypotheses are not necessarily excluding. They could be complementary.

4.15. Study Limitations and Strength

We must acknowledge several limitations to this work. First, as commented in the FCP, our approach to determine whether a CE5thK is authentic is not a gold standard of reference to validate our findings externally. The authentic CE5thK event itself cannot be performed and replicated upon demand or be controlled in a laboratory setting. We only can imagine a time machine to verify what happened in the place and the data alleged in each alleged contact with ETI. Due to non-reproducible nature of this phenomenon, it is more akin to a fact in a criminal case. On the other hand, internally the setting of objective criteria worked as validation tools to decide authenticity when the alleged CE5thK met all the subjective criteria. We admit that our conclusion about authenticity is only probabilistic as high or low. Our probability is not 100 percent, and we recognize that truth in science is probabilistic. We have no absolute truth. In medicine, 2 decades ago the correct treatment for cardiac arrest outside the hospital was mouth-to-mouth resuscitation and cardiac massage. Today it has changed, and only cardiac massage is recommended because it was discovered that mouth-to-mouth breathing lowers chances of surviving. Each one of our six objective criteria serve as strength of hard evidence because each adds proof. Still, we decided that the high bar of meeting 6 subjective criteria and at least 1

objective criteria by at least 2 independent researchers was necessary to maintain a high probability of each case being authentic. We discarded most of alleged contactees with less than high scores, showing it is not easy to meet our cutoff to be considered a contactee of high probability to be authentic. Additionally, due to the dynamic nature of the work, a new source of information might appear about the CE5thK cases irrespective of our current categorization. We leave open the eventual possibility that any of these cases could change categorization with the appearance of new evidence.

Second, in spite of intent and effort to decrease subjectivity to a minimum, setting the 12 criteria-rule of evaluation necessarily contains a degree of subjectivity in the scoring of subjective criteria as discussed above because of the nature of the subject matter studied and the component qualitative of study design. The consensus about the final categorization by two or more independent researchers at least lowers the degree of subjectivity. Third, the information of technical, biological, and social nature received by authentic 'contactees' are simply presented, as our study did not have the ability to dig deep into details. We can't give information more specific because it was not available from the contactees. We can speculate that it could be intentional by the ETI in order to not influence directly the destiny of humanity. In addition, specific information could put the contactees at risk, in the face of the clear interest from enterprises or governments to gain political and military advantage from such specific knowledge.

The strength of our work in the EP is in the fact of finding additional new authentic CE5thK cases that support the first findings in the FCP. Both studies support our hypothesis that contact from ETI with humanity is happening, but the percentage of authentic 'contactees' could be lower with time passing. Any eventual polemics or criticism on the validity of our results must be directed individually to each case. In addition, the richness of scientific and technical information received by authentic 'contactees' and discussed here means a milestone in the scientific literature.

4.16. Implications and Applications

The FCP gives three great contributions to science. First, it created an original approach to determine the authenticity of alleged CE5thK. Second, it tested and supported the hypothesis that extraterrestrial contact with humanity is happening on the Earth. Finally, it found scientific and technical information received from authentic 'contactees' with revolutionary impacts for society. The more recent EP provided three additional contributions. First, the EP further supported our hypothesis that true advanced contact with ETI occurs, but as time goes on, is more difficult to identify. Second, it shows that a new research team could be similarly and satisfactorily trained in order to apply the method in a new series. This suggests that similar studies could be carried out on other continents, and have a good chance of validating alleged 'contactees' from different cultures or languages. Finally, it gives more and original technical and scientific information from both studies. This could mean a "Know-how" process a way of 'technology transfer', allowing us to hypothesize and speculate about the implications from the information that was systematized and classified in order to see patterns of concordance.

Almost 10 years ago, at the 2013 Economic Forum at Davos, it was predicted that the discovery of ETI, as one of five "X factors" - emerging concerns of possible future importance and with unknown consequences - would certainly be one of the biggest news stories and interest would be intense. The discovery's largest near-term impact would likely be on science itself [116]. We ask if the moment is today? The Pentagon recently recognized the encounters of planes with UFOs and a historic American Congressional hearing was carried out focusing on military reports of UFOs. In this context, the findings of this study supporting advanced contact from ETI with human beings, and all information about social-economical organization, type of recommended food, interdimensional gates, time travel and other kinds of knowledge identified in our study, definitely could challenge key paradigms in several fields of science and knowledge.

It is virtually certain that many other authentic CE5thK cases exist around the world, still to be discovered. These cases likely have even more new scientific information to understand. The deeper analysis of information received by authentic contacts and eventual practical application merits additional research. New studies will be necessary to get a better understanding and meaning of the phenomenon of advanced extraterrestrial contact. We consider that these studies open a door to complex knowledge for the human mind.

5. Conclusion

Our study confirmed that the twelve-criterion method could be successfully used by a new trained team of researchers to conduct additional studies anywhere in the world. We also found evidence to support that advanced contact from ETI with human beings on the Earth is continuing, but each time it is more difficult to identify authentic 'contactees' due to the growing number of false 'contactees'. The richness of new technical and scientific information received by authentic 'contactees' in their respective CE5thK, represents critical and revolutionary information with amazing

potential for our society in several fields of knowledge. This knowledge needs further study in order to develop and apply to the critical problems that are leading to risk of mankind's extinction. We believe that the moment to act is now.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

All the authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Statement of informed consent

We did not consider necessary the informed consent of the alleged 'contactees' due to all these individuals had publicly assured having been contacted physically or mentally with an ETI and there was some information received from them, therefore this research is focused about a specific matter of public domain. Additionally, some of alleged 'contactees' were not contacted by us directly and in others cases they were dead.

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